

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE TECHNOLOGY OF
TEACHING CHILDREN THROUGH PLAY IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL
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Abstract. *This article discusses the methods of using didactic games for the development of children's thinking, the help of didactic games to develop the speech of preschool children, to familiarize them with the environment and nature.*

Keywords: *preschool age, thinking, child, didactic games, game, child, preschool education.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются методы использования дидактических игр для развития мышления детей, роль дидактических игр в развитии речи детей дошкольного возраста, в ознакомлении их с окружающим миром и природой.*

Ключевые слова: *дошкольный возраст, мышление, ребенок, дидактические игры, игра, ребенок, дошкольное образование.*

The main goal of the reforms being carried out in our country is to bring up the future successors as smart, intelligent, well-rounded people in all respects. In preschool educational organizations, it is required to organize each lesson by enriching the world of mental thinking of children of the new age. The knowledge acquired in preschool education, the first worldview formed, the acquired skills and qualifications serve as the main criterion for the next period of a person's life.

At present, the need to master a foreign language is dictated by the modern social order of society, which is caused by the growth of intercultural contacts in all spheres of human activity.

The study of a foreign language at school begins in the junior grade, and from that moment the whole learning process acquires communicative orientation. The methodology of teaching a foreign language in elementary school is still in its infancy, today the search for effective methods of teaching a foreign language in junior school, which are based on the psychological characteristics of students at this stage is actively carried out. It is already proved that the leading methods of teaching elementary school students are game methods. English is an international language; it is spoken in many countries, on several continents and in different parts of the world.

Nowadays, most people know English and speak it fluently. There are different reasons for this: some people want to travel, others need this knowledge to build a successful career, some learn for the sake of interest, in modern conditions of globalization people want to communicate with people from other countries, etc. Modern society is on the way of humanization of education.

Humanization of education implies the organization of the learning process, which would correspond to the unity of social and professional development of the individual, taking into account personal needs. Among the humanistic tendencies of the real learning process, the most important is the orientation to the development of personality. The more harmoniously the personality is developed, the freer a person is in the realization of personal functions. Interest is the basis of learning activity, as it occupies the main place in the learning process.

Interest is the basis of learning activity, as it occupies the main place in increasing motivation and learning stamina. It is interest that stimulates the student emotionally, cognitively, linguistically, contributing to the effective formation of foreign language communicative competence [1]. Low communicative motivation is caused by the wrong approach to the personality of the pupil, his psycho-emotional construction, and the construction of his personal motivation sphere. This suggests that at the lesson it is necessary to work not at the level of "the student himself", but at the level of his abilities and properties, finding and developing them. Thus, in a modern school the main task of a teacher is to find ways to make greater use of individual abilities, abilities and personal characteristics of students. It is unacceptable to ignore the personal characteristics, features of psycho-emotional organization and communicative development of students.

Determinants of communicative motivation, acting as the main internal reserves of personality, should be activated in foreign language lessons, they are the main tools of pedagogical influence in teaching and education in modern society. When children enter school, their leading activity changes from play to learning. But since this change of processes is gradual, junior schoolchildren like to participate in educational games at lessons. To see the unusual in the ordinary, junior schoolchildren like to compose, invent, fantasize, incarnate. The game, for junior schoolchildren, is a kind of means of self-expression, self-determination, self-testing and self-fulfillment. At the initial stage of learning a foreign language there is a great attraction to this subject, but for a number of objective and subjective reasons, the subject loses its attractiveness, many consider it one of the most difficult and, therefore, unloved. Children of primary school age have great advantages in learning a foreign language: natural curiosity, well-developed longterm and visual imaginative memory, impressionability, emotionality, great activity. Didactic value of the game proved K.D. Ushinsky [2]: - Game is an independent form of developmental activity for children of different ages. - Children's game is the freest form of their activity, which is the realization, the study of the surrounding world, a wide space for personal creativity, activity of self-discovery, self-expression is opened. - Game is the first stage of a child's activity, the first school of his behavior, normative and equal activity of junior schoolchildren, adolescents, youth, their goals change with the growth of pupils. - Game is practice of development. Children play for the sake of their development, and they develop for the sake of their play. - Game is the freedom of self-disclosure, of self-development, based on the subconscious, on reason and on creativity. - Game is the main sphere of children's communication, it is where interpersonal problems are solved, human relations get experienced. Games are a powerful stimulus for language learning and an effective technique in the foreign language teacher's arsenal. The use of a game and the ability to create language situations makes students ready, willing and able to play and communicate. In a modern school that focuses on activating and intensifying the learning process, game activities are used in the following cases: 1. As an independent method for mastering a certain subject; 2. As an element (sometimes very important) of another method; 3. As an entire lesson or part of it (introduction, explanation, reinforcement, control or practice); 4. In the organization of an extracurricular activity [3]. Thus, it is worth mentioning that a learning game is a specially organized task. It requires the tension of emotional and mental forces. In other words, a learning game is an exercise that helps in consolidation, control and correction of knowledge, skills and abilities, creates pedagogical

visibility in the study of specific material. It creates conditions for active thinking. Game is a task containing learning task, stimulating intellectual activity of students, teaching prediction, research, checking correctness of made decisions. Classification of games in foreign language teaching takes different approaches. All classifications to date have been very conditional. Several classifications of educational games will be considered. Ж. Piaget distinguishes three main types of games, which he correlates with developing stages of children [4]: Exercising games – the child's first games related to grasping, acting with toys (the first year of life); Symbolic games, which are based on the imitation of the adult world by means of a special system of symbols (early preschool age); Rules-based games, which are roleplaying games. The following classification of educational games for use in foreign language teaching can also be considered to be successful: - Preparatory games. - Creative games. Grammar, lexical, phonetic and spelling games contribute to the formation of new skills. Preparatory games "build" the foundation of the language. Without grammatical structures, vocabulary, phonetics and spelling, the language cannot be mastered. And monotonous and unsatisfying training can be replaced by games and playful situations, which will help to make boring work more interesting and exciting. Further development of language skills and abilities is the purpose of creative games. They are a training tool for the student's ability to use language skills creatively. They can also be used when reviewing material.

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